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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Ranking of performance degrading mechanisms for hadron storage rings and synchrotrons

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ABSTRACT

We survey the performance degrading mechanisms for hadron storage rings and synchrotrons. The various processes causing performance degradation in past, existing and planned facilities are compiled and classified, along with the most commonly employed mitigation measures. Both the limiting mechanisms and the mitigations are ranked according to their respective importance as presently perceived.

ARIES Consortium, 2019

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

The results of several ARIES WP6 workshops, in particular APEC2018 held in December 2018, and of a subsequent community survey enable a ranking of the performance degrading mechanisms for hadron storage rings and synchrotrons. In this report, we compile and classify the processes causing performance degradation in past, existing and planned facilities, and evaluate their respective importance. Beam loss, single-bunch instabilities, and nonlinearities are the most prominent limiting effects. We also discuss the commonly employed mitigation measures. Landau octupoles, bunch-by-bunch feedback, optimised tunes, and tailored slippage factor are most significant, while novel techniques are emerging.

1. Introduction

ARIES aims at improving the present and future performance of the European particle accelerator infrastructure, thereby strengthening Europe's leading position in this field. Among its several fields of activity, ARIES is strongly engaged on the "energy frontier" as the most visible and popularized because extending this frontier is a principal towards future scientific discoveries in particle physics; in addition, ARIES networking leadership also spearheads advances on the "intensity frontier".

European leadership, gained by providing the global research community with the Large Hadron Collider at CERN, has triggered a quest for higher-energy hadron accelerators. However, moving beyond the state-of-the-art will require exciting developments in high-field magnets and other technologies. Similarly, the energy reach of linear lepton colliders is dictated by the electric field gradient that can be achieved in the accelerating structures. The intensity/luminosity frontier is particularly complex because it is related to both technological and beam physics aspects, which, in turn, are closely related to the specific type of accelerator.

The role of the ARIES networks is of a catalysing nature to circumvent, and reverse, the natural fragmentation into specialties and domains, to break barriers between traditional communities, and to aggregate a wide community around topics of excellence. The WP6 on Accelerator Performance and Concepts (APEC) is an ARIES networking activity, which strives for the ultimate performance in existing facilities and, especially, in future accelerators that are now in an advanced phase of planning or construction. APEC pursues this goal by investigating advanced beam stabilization techniques, novel collimation schemes and reliability enhancement measures. Specifically, the ARIES task 6.2 examines the Beam Quality Control in Hadron Storage Rings and Synchrotrons. This task has organized a series of workshops in order to bring experts from several institutions together and to discuss the state of the art in beam quality control in hadron storage rings and synchrotrons.

Most relevant for the present report, were the following APEC networking events:

1. **ICFA mini-Workshop on Impedances and Beam Instabilities in Particle Accelerators** Benevento 19-22 September 2017 (<http://prewww.unisannio.it/workshopwakefields2017/>)
2. **Space Charge 2017** workshop, Darmstadt, 4-6 Oct. 2017 (<https://indico.gsi.de/event/5600/>).
3. **Slow Extraction** workshop, CERN, 9-11 Nov. 2017 (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/639766/>).
4. **Pulse Power for Kicker Systems (PULPOKS)** Workshop, CERN, 12-14 March 2018 (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/682148/>).

5. 2nd CERN Space Charge Collaboration meeting, CERN, 12-14 March 2018 (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/688897/>).
6. International Workshop on **Electron Cloud Effects in Accelerators** (ELOUD'18), La Biodola, Italy, 6-7 June 2018 (<https://agenda.infn.it/conferenceDisplay.py?confId=13351>).
7. **APEC2018** workshop, Frankfurt am Main, Germany, 10-12 December 2018 (<https://indico.gsi.de/event/7510/>).

2. Mechanisms and effects impacting beam quality

Synchrotrons and storage rings are the main devices used in most accelerator laboratories to deliver beams to experiments. The mode of utilisation of circular accelerators strongly depends on the requests of the users. The worldwide competition between experimenters has given rise to highly specialized laboratories, where the application of acceleration or storage schemes is specific to the respective needs. In spite of this specialization and fragmentation, a number of common areas and concepts exist. For example, we can distinguish between intensity limitations and brightness limitations. In this section, we briefly list and discuss relevant performance-limiting mechanisms which apply to most, if not all, the hadron accelerators.

2.1 MAIN INTENSITY LIMITATIONS

- **Injector:** Injectors are the part of an accelerator chain used to prepare, e.g. accumulate, cool and accelerate, the charged particle beams for subsequent injection into a synchrotron or storage ring. The performance and limitations imposed by the beam physics and technology in the injectors can become an important factor limiting the beam intensity or the beam brightness (intensity divided by transverse emittance) in circular machines. The intensity and stability of hadrons depends on their energy and on their charge state.
- **RF power:** The RF power exchanged between the beam and the RF system becomes significant when the average beam intensity is pushed to the limit. Radio frequency (rf) and low-level rf (LLRF) systems are usually configured to minimize transient beam loading effects.
- **Single bunch instability:** Under this term, several different types of instabilities are subsumed, such as (longitudinal) Robinson instability; negative mass instability; resistive wall instability; microwave instability; head-tail instability; longitudinal head-tail instability; and transverse mode coupling instability (TMCI). See ref. [1].
- **Multi-bunch instability:** multi-bunch instabilities occur when the wake field excited by a passing bunch persists long enough to affect the bunch coming next to the location of the impedance. This typically happens for narrow band impedances, e.g. cavities with a high Q value. See ref. [1].

- **Collimation:** The presence of a collimation system is essential to allow the intensity increase and to localize the associated beam losses. In fact, by increasing the intensity more beam will unavoidably get lost; hence in order to meet safety requirement (1W/m for hands-on maintenance), or to prevent quenches of superconducting magnets, it is necessary to deposit the runaway particles in dedicated hot spots, on sufficiently robust material. The capability of absorbing uncontrolled beam loss is a limiting factor on the path towards high intensity. This includes the allowed material damage (depending on the ion species, intensity and energy), and the collimation scheme. According to the type of accelerator, the work load of a collimation system varies: for LHC, given the very high energy of the stored beam particles, an extremely high collimation efficiency is required, as is an extreme robustness of the primary and secondary collimators, which will be hit by a number of bunches in case of expected machine failures, such as an asynchronous beam dump. See Ref. [2].
- **Electron Cloud:** When bunches travel through bend magnets, synchrotron radiation is emitted, which, in turn, after hitting the pipe causes the emission of electrons from the beam pipe wall. Also residual gas molecules can be ionized by the beam, liberating free electrons. All these newly generated electrons may get accelerated in the transverse electric field of the beam and hit the beam pipe (again) with significant kinetic energy, resulting in secondary emission. The generated electron cloud affects the bunch motion, and, when dense enough, may lead to beam instabilities. In addition to affecting the beam, the electron cloud will unavoidably deposit on the vacuum chambers a significant energy, leading to an extra work load for the cryogenic system, in case the beam pipe is located inside superconducting magnets. The capability of the cryogenic system becomes a limit, due to the electron cloud, of the achievable beam intensity. The seriousness of the electron cloud strongly depends on the beam-pipe surface properties, the beam pipe dimensions, the bunch spacing, and the bunch intensity. See Ref. [3].
- **Beam loss:** Uncontrolled beam losses may be caused by not well-understood mechanisms. For example, in the LHC a weakly populated halo is constantly formed, under the influence of the beam-beam collisions and perhaps external noise. This halo must constantly be removed by the collimation system. The combination of multiple effects which taken alone would not be significant may lead to a background of beam loss which sets a limit to the total intensity that an accelerator may digest.
- **Dynamic Aperture:** The dynamic aperture (DA), i.e. the stable region in the beam-particle phase space, results from the nonlinear forces in the accelerator. These forces arise from the magnets' nonlinear components. The main result of the nonlinear dynamics is that a particle at a certain amplitude will get lost on the beam pipe. According to the type of accelerator and the length over which a beam should be stored, the dynamic aperture becomes a critical aspect. This is true especially in colliders (LHC) and storage rings. Mitigation strategies to improve DA are difficult to be implement. See [4].

- **Momentum Acceptance:** This feature designates the maximum deviation of the momentum of a particle from the reference particle accepted by an RF bucket, or limited by a physical aperture (i.e. the finite vacuum chamber at a place of nonzero dispersion) or by the off-momentum nonlinear dynamics. The momentum acceptance may become a limiting intensity factor in the sense that one cannot put into the available longitudinal phase space an arbitrarily large number of particles.

2.2 MAIN BRIGHTNESS LIMITATIONS

- **IBS:** Intra-beam scattering (IBS) refers to the multiple small-angle collisions of the particles in a beam off each other. The resulting macroscopic effect is a particle diffusion and beam-size growth in both the transverse and the longitudinal beam dimensions. This effect becomes particularly significant for storage rings and colliders, where the long time of beam storage allows an otherwise small growth rate to noticeably impact the beam emittance, and to, hence cause, a reduction of brightness. See [5].
- **Space Charge:** The collective nature of the Coulomb force manifests itself also as a counter part of the IBS. The dynamics of a beam particle is affected by the macroscopic electromagnetic field of the beam. This produces a nonlinear defocusing force, which, for intense beams, affects the focusing properties defined by the accelerator lattice. The main effect of the space charge is to alter the betatron tunes. An overlap of the space charge tune-spread with an important machine resonance causes emittance blow-up. Also the matching of a high intensity beam with the accelerator is rendered more complex by the space charge forces, and if the matching condition is not met, coherent envelope oscillations may eventually lead to emittance increase. Typically the effect of space charge is significant for space charge tune-shifts of order $\Delta Q \sim 0.5$. See [6].
- **Nonlinearities:** Magnet nonlinearities, but also nonlinear forces in the longitudinal plane, are source of beam filamentation in 6D phase space. The resulting effect is the increase of the beam emittance. The coupling of nonlinearities with the accelerator periodicity may excite a resonance dynamics. Transverse resonances of type $N_x Q_x + N_y Q_y = m$ (where $Q_{x,y}$ denote the two betatron tunes, and $N_{x,y}$ plus m are integers), may considerably constrain the available working point in betatron tune space. A subtler but equally significant effect is the nonlinear amplitude-dependent detuning. In bunched beams, the coupling of the longitudinal motion with space charge and transverse resonances also creates a relevant beam diffusion, which reduces the beam brightness or leads to beam loss.
- **Beta-beating:** A large brightness is a fundamental requirement to reach the luminosity in large collider such as LHC. Small beam sizes are fundamental; hence, the beam optics must be carefully controlled. On the other hand, on large colliders the number of quadrupoles is large, hence enhancing the effect of small errors in each quadrupole gradient. It turns out that, as a net effect, the beta function oscillates around the nominal one producing a sort of beating. This effect increases with the number of quadrupoles as \sqrt{N} . For large colliders, this effect can be detrimental and must be carefully controlled. A matching of the beta functions (or

beam sizes) of two colliding beams at the collision point is important in view of the beam-beam effect. See [7]

- **Beam-beam:** In colliders, when the two beams rotating in opposite direction collide, one beam is subject to the strong nonlinear field of the other beam. High luminosity requires the optical functions at the interaction point to be very small. Several effects are attributed to the beam-beam interaction such as a nonlinear amplitude dependent detuning of the particles of one beam, as well as dynamic changes in beta function and dynamic changes in the emittance. Similar to the space charge force, the beam-beam interaction also increases the tune spread, but in addition, due to the localized nature of the collision and the extremely nonlinear force, the beam-beam collisions strongly excite nonlinear resonances up to very high order. Empirically a limit of $\Delta Q \sim 0.01-0.02$ for the maximum total beam-beam induced tune spread in hadron colliders has been observed. To reach or overcome this limit, a careful choice of the working points is necessary for avoiding coherent beam-beam instabilities and harmful incoherent resonances, which can be of an order as high as 20. For long bunches, the beta function changes during the collision, longitudinal motion is strongly coupled to the transverse motion, resulting in additional particle losses or beam halo [8].
- **Injector:** Space charge effects are also important in the injectors. Since the beam energy normally is lower in the injector, often these limitations are more stringent than in the higher energy machines, and the achievable beam brightness is defined by the injector.

2.3 OTHER SOURCE OF PERFORMANCE LIMITATIONS

- **Dynamic vacuum:** A good vacuum is of fundamental importance for beam lifetime. A dynamic vacuum pressure increase can be caused by beam-ion stripping due to collisions with residual gas molecules. The consequent loss of beam particles then yields a release of secondary molecules or ions from the surface of the beam pipe. The resulting combined effect may lead to vacuum instability or a local pressure bump. If the ion species, at the relevant beam energy, has a critically high interaction cross-section with the residual gas molecules, or if the beam-pipe surface has a significant desorption yield, considerable beam loss couples to the dynamic vacuum, and enhances the demand on beam control [9].
- **Beam loss:** Here the term beam loss is used in a generic way. In an accelerator system, the presence of unwanted and not well understood beam loss is an indicator of performance limitations. Under certain circumstances, empirical studies set limits of beam loss, and in turn the full availability of the beam is limited by “beam loss”.
- **Collimation:** This performance limitation is also somehow related to the capability of the collimation system to capture halo particles. According to an accelerator’s operating regime and to the type of beam, the demand on the collimation system can vary. For LHC the high energy of the beam requires extremely conservative criteria on the capability of the collimation system to remove protons at too large amplitudes. For the FAIR project the

collimation system also has to capture halo particles, but at the same time the FAIR collimators must exhibit a limited secondary emission yield in order to avoid creating vacuum degradation processes, and local dynamic vacuum increases, which ultimately affect the beam lifetime [10].

- **Quenches:** This term refers to the local loss of superconductivity in SC magnets due to energy deposition in the superconducting cables. The energy is mainly deposited by local beam loss or by thermal radiation from impedance heating effect or from an electron cloud. Also eddy currents may become a concern. Quenches are harmful because the loss of superconductivity causes the sudden loss of the beam, which may create severe damage to the accelerator structure according to the energy stored in the beam. Usually if a quench is detected an efficient safety system triggers a rapid beam abort to protect the accelerator components, but an increased rate of beam-induced quenches will limit the overall performance of the beam delivery as the restoring of the magnet and cryogenic properties requires significant amounts of time. Frequent quenches can also lead to premature aging and damage of the superconducting magnets [11].
- **Halo development:** Beam halo may develop due to several effects, such as power-converter ripple and noise in hardware, space charge, and nonlinearities. Sometimes the sources of halo formation are very difficult to pin down. The general consequence is that long-term beam storage is significantly affected by halo formation. Usually the collimation system is designed to capture the halo particle
- **Spill structure:** For some experiments, beam is stored in a synchrotron or storage ring, and delivered to the experiment as a slow flux of beam particles. The experiment usually requires a high regularity, uniformity and reproducibility of beam particle flux in order to reach the maximum detection efficiency. The slow extraction is obtained by exciting the third order resonance and implementing an operation scheme that continually leads some beam particles to cross the separatrix, so that a slow spill of the beam is obtained. The time structure of this beam is a characteristic of the accelerator/beam performance. Several causes or effects determine the quality of the “spill structure”, for example, noises and ripple of the hardware power converters, the characteristics of the accelerator optics at the extraction section, the control of the nonlinear dynamics and of the nonlinear detuning, and intensity effects such as space charge [12].
- **Peak luminosity or luminosity lifetime:** In colliders the beam lifetime is limited not only by beam interaction with the residual gas, nonlinear dynamics, external noise, and space charge, but also by the interaction of the beam with another beam (beam-beam). These interactions create a diffusion which ultimately leads particle to leave the beam core and get lost, or forming a halo. The effect on the beam is a reduction of the number of particles in the beam, which decays exponentially or algebraically with the storage time. The unavoidable beam loss due to inelastic beam-beam collisions is to be included in the beam lifetime equations (the

inverse of the sum of the inverse beam lifetimes of each individual effect corresponds to the lifetime of the integrated effect).

- UFO/dust:** ‘Unidentified Falling Objects’ (UFOs) are allegedly the source of mysterious fast beam losses and rapid beam dumps at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). UFO candidates are dust particles, which fall into the beam trajectory so as to cause uncontrolled beam loss and, hence, trigger a beam dump. More than thousand UFO events have been recorded during LHC operations. Most of the UFOs do not result in a beam dump. Possible sources of these hypothetical dust particles are distributed ion pumps, electrical discharges, and movable devices; recently strong indication emerged that gas condensate at cold elements may be a significant source of neutral molecules. The presence of these mysterious objects may become a significant source of performance degradation. Prior to the LHC, “dust trapping” affecting the beam lifetime had only be seen with negatively charged beams (antiprotons, positrons).

3. Ranking of the mechanisms and effects impacting the beam quality

In this chapter we present a ranking of the mechanisms presented in the previous chapter. The ranking has been made via a community survey. We have received expert feedback from seven laboratories – Fermilab, BNL, CERN, SLAC/SSRL, J-PARC, INFN-LNF, GSI – who ranked the effects according to their operational experience. In order to document the terms of this ranking and the actual user landscape, Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of the accelerators and beams of the institutions participating in the ranking effort.

Laboratory	Accelerator name	Accelerator Circumference (m)	Initial/final Energy (GeV)	Particles per bunch	Rms bunch length (cm)	Ramp time (s)/ stored time (s)
Fermilab	Booster	476	0.4/8	5E10	30	0.033
BNL	RHIC	3834	25/255	2E11	0.6	300/3600
CERN	SPS	7000	26/450	1.1E11	15	5/20
SLAC/SSRL	SPEAR3	234	3	8.7E9	0.6	NA
J-PARC	Main ring	1567.5	3/30	3.3E13	1500	1.4/0~2
INFN-LNF	DAFNE	97	510	1E11	1.06	0/1200
GSI	ESR	108	0.4/0.004	1E8	200	10/2000
GSI	SIS18/SIS100	216/1000	0.011/2.7	5E11	3000	0.5

Table 1: Summary of the accelerator characteristics and main beam features at the laboratories participating in the ranking effort.

3.1 RANKING OF THE MAIN INTENSITY LIMITATIONS

In the following, we rank the main intensity limitations. This ranking was obtained from the answers given by the participants in the APEC survey, on a scale from 1 (of no or low importance) to 5 (highly important).

- Injector and RF power:**

Figure 1: These two histograms show the ranking of the two intensity limitation factors “injector” and “RF power”. The left picture has an average of 2.6; the right picture has an average of 2.75.

- Single bunch instability and Multi-bunch instability:**

Figure 2: The ranking of single and multi-bunch instabilities. The left picture has an average of 2.75; the right picture has an average of 2.75.

- **Collimation and Electron Cloud:**

Figure 3: Ranking of the Collimation and Electron Cloud; the left picture has an average ranking of 2.25; also the right picture has an average ranking of 2.25.

- **Beam loss and Dynamic Aperture, and Momentum Acceptance**

Figure 4: Here we show the ranking of 3 effects – beam loss, dynamics aperture, and momentum acceptance. The left picture has an average ranking of 3.125; the central picture an average ranking of 2.37; the right picture an average ranking of 2.25

3.2 SUMMARY OF THE RANKING OF INTENSITY LIMITATIONS

The results of this survey are not easy to interpret. Due to the broad difference in the laboratories participating, from this survey no strong dominant intensity limitation emerges. In order to interpret the survey, we compute from each source of intensity limitation the average ranking, and its standard deviation. The average indicates a global degree of **relevance** on the scale 1-5. The standard deviation instead gives an indication of the **global impact** of an effect: if the standard deviation is small, it means many laboratories are equally affected – or equally unaffected – , by that effect. If instead the standard deviation is large (maximum 2 for this survey), then it means that this effect impacts one or two laboratories in particular, but not the other laboratories. Therefore, the smaller the standard deviation the more global is the effect.

From the aforementioned results, we conclude that **Beam Loss** is an important intensity limitation source, but it is relevant only for a few laboratories. Instead **Single bunch instabilities** and **dynamic aperture** are somewhat less critical, but of a broader impact to many laboratories.

*Table 1 Table 2: Left: Ranking of each intensity limitation by **relevance**. Right: Ranking of the intensity limitation by **global impact**.*

R	Intensity limitation	ave	std	R	Intensity limitation	ave	std
1	Beam loss	3.12	1.16	1	Single bunch instability	2.75	0.82
2	RF Power	2.75	1.2	2	DA	2.375	0.99
3	Single bunch instability	2.75	0.82	3	Collimation	2.25	1.09
4	Multi-bunch instability	2.75	1.56	4	Beam loss	3.12	1.16
5	Injector	2.6	1.6	5	RF Power	2.75	1.2
6	DA	2.375	0.99	6	Momentum Acceptance	2.25	1.2
7	Collimation	2.25	1.09	7	E-Cloud	2.25	1.3
8	Momentum Acceptance	2.25	1.2	8	Multi-bunch instability	2.75	1.56
9	E-Cloud	2.25	1.3	9	Injector	2.6	1.6

3.3 RANKING THE MAIN BRIGHTNESS LIMITATIONS

In this section we present a detailed review of the ranking of the main brightness limitations.

- **Nonlinearities and Beta-beating**

Figure 5: Ranking of the nonlinearities and beta-beating; the left ranking has an average of 3.625, the right ranking and average of 2.5.

- **Beam-beam, Injectors**

Figure 6: Ranking of the beam-beam effect, and the injectors; the left ranking has an average of 2, the right ranking an average of 2.5.

- **IBS and Space Charge**

Figure 7: Ranking of the Intra-beam Scattering (IBS), and of the space charge effects; the left picture features an average ranking of 1.75, the right picture an average ranking of 3.125.

3.4 SUMMARY OF THE RANKING OF BRIGHTNESS LIMITATIONS

We summarize the rankings of brightness limitations in Table 3, using the same criteria as discussed in Section 3.2. It is interesting to note that the **Nonlinearities** are ranked both as the most relevant and also are of concern for most of the laboratories. Instead the “**Space Charge**” has a high relevance (difficulty of treatment and study), but is of concern only for a few machines, which are those that operate with high intensity beams. These results also show that IBS is considered to be a topic of limited relevance (suggesting everything has been understood about this topic).

*Table 3: Left: Ranking of each brightness limitation by **relevance**. Right: Ranking of the brightness limitations by **global impact**.*

R	Intensity limitation	ave	std
1	Nonlinearities	3.625	0.99
2	Space charge	3.125	1.53
3	Beta-beating	2.5	1.3
4	Injector	2.5	1.75
5	Beam-beam	2.0	1.41
6	IBS	1.75	1.39

R	Intensity limitation	ave	Std
1	Nonlinearities	3.625	0
2	Beta-beating	2.5	1.3
3	Beam-beam	2.0	1.41
4	IBS	1.75	1.39
5	Space charge	3.125	1.53
6	Injector	2.5	1.75

3.5 OTHER SOURCE OF PERFORMANCE LIMITATIONS

For completeness we rank the sources of performance limitations which are more specific, and considered as special cases.

- **Dynamic vacuum and Beam Loss**

Figure 8: Ranking of the Dynamic vacuum and of the Beam loss; the left picture shows an average ranking of 2.37; the right picture a ranking of 3.37

- **Collimation and Quenches**

Figure 9: Ranking of collimation and of quenches; the average ranking in the left picture is 2.37; the average ranking in the right picture 1.37.

- **Halo development and Spill structure**

Figure 10: Ranking of mechanisms halo development and spill structure. The left picture features and average ranking of 2.37; the right picture an average ranking of 1.37.

Figure 11: Assessment of Peak luminosity/luminosity lifetime, and UFO/dust. The left picture features an average ranking of 2.12, the right picture an average ranking of 1.12.

3.6 SUMMARY OF OTHER SOURCES OF PERFORMANCE LIMITATIONS

The above results, summarized in Table 4, show that **Quenches** and **UFO/dust** are ranked on the last position in terms of relevance; probably this means that these source of intensity limitations are treated through an established technology or methodology or are of no relevance for most facilities. The same two effects have a low standard deviation among all laboratories participating in the survey. which, in this case – given the low average ranking – does not reflect a broad impact, but a broad non-impact. **Beam Loss** is instead having a high relevance because it is very difficult to control and to predict, however, this source of intensity limitation is of concern only to some of the laboratories.

*Table 4: Left: Ranking of each of the other performance limitations by **relevance**. Right: Ranking of the other performance limitations by **global impact**.*

R	Other performance limitation	ave	std
1	Beam loss	3.37	1.21
2	Halo development	2.5	1.22
3	Collimation	2.37	1.21
4	Dynamic vacuum	2.37	1.4
5	Peak luminosity	2.12	1.53
6	Spill. Structure	2.0	1.73
7	Quenches	1.37	0.69
8	UFO/dust	1.12	0.33

R	Other performance limitation	ave	std
1	UFO/dust	1.12	0.33
2	Quenches	1.37	0.69
3	Beam loss	3.37	1.21
4	Collimation	2.37	1.21
5	Halo development	2.5	1.22
6	Dynamic vacuum	2.37	1.4
7	Peak luminosity	2.12	1.53
8	Spill. Structure	2.0	1.73

4. Mitigation survey and ranking

In the spirit of the APEC 6.2 task, in addition to the ranking of the sources of beam degradation we investigated how the community deals with these problems. The mitigation strategies are the result of the understanding of the mechanism and of the technology employed to implement those strategies. Therefore, it becomes natural to rank the present mitigation strategies as an assessment directly arising from the - in the field experience - from the several laboratories that participated to the survey for ranking the mechanisms degrading the beam quality. Consistently we proceed by summarizing the mitigation strategies and later to rank them.

4.1 MITIGATION METHODS EMPLOYED

In the following we summarize the mitigation methods employed by the laboratories participating to the mechanism survey.

- **Feedback Systems**

Figure 12: This picture illustrates which type of feedback system is used. The majority of the laboratories employ a bunch-by-bunch feedback system.

- **Landau Damping**

Figure 13: Methods based on Landau damping are implemented mainly via classical octupole approach and with 2nd order chromaticity. RF quadrupoles appears as an emerging technique.

- **Special Optics**

Figure 14: Mitigation methods relying on special optics are popular in the community.

- **Polarization Control**

Figure 15: Polarization control is a technique necessary only at those few laboratories, whose operation requires polarized beams. Only a single participant assessed the use of the three techniques named on the horizontal axis.

4.2 RANKING OF THE MITIGATION METHODS EMPLOYED

Following the same approach as for the performance limitations, in the previous chapter, we rank the mitigation methods computing both the average and standard deviation.

- Ranking of mitigation methods based on Feedback Systems**

Figure 16: This picture shows the ranking of three different types of feedback system, with the following result: Bunch-by-bunch = 3; narrow band = 1.75; intrabunch = 2.0.

- Ranking of mitigation methods based on Landau damping**

Figure 17: This picture shows the ranking of Landau damping mitigations methods, with the following result: Octupole = 2.87; e-lens = 1.125; RF-Quad=1.25; 2-nd order = 2.0.

- **Ranking of mitigation methods based on Special Optics**

Figure 18: In this picture we show the ranking of the first 4 methods of mitigation based on special optics. The ranking is the following: IOTA = 1.25; IBS = 1.37; Optics for inst. = 1.44; ATS = 1.25

Figure 19: This picture continues the ranking of the mitigation methods based on a special optics: IBS suppression = 1.25; low-beta = 1.5; neg-alpha = 2.0; special slippage = 2.0; special tune = 2.1.

- **Ranking of the mitigations based on cooling**

Figure 20: This picture ranks the mitigation methods based on various cooling techniques: stochastic = 1.37; electron = 1.37; coherent = 1.0.

Figure 21: This picture ranks additional mitigation methods based on other types of cooling. Laser cooling = 1; optical = 1.25.

- **Ranking of the polarization control mitigation methods**

Figure 22: For this category, 7 participants responded with “not applicable” as polarization is not an issue at their laboratories.

Figure 23: Tune jump and partial Siberian snake find no use by anyone.

Figure 24: Optics and momentum control obtain rank 3, while transverse emittance control ranks at 5, based on a single respondent.

4.3 SUMMARY OF RANKING OF MITIGATION METHODS

Using the same procedure as in Chapter 3, we now summarize and rank the mitigation methods. The results are shown in the following tables.

*Table 5: Ranking of each of the mitigation methods based on feedback. In this case, **relevance** and global **impact** figure of merit provide the same overall ranking.*

R	Mitigation based on feedback	ave	std
1	Bunch-by-bunch	3.0	1.5
2	Intrabunch	2.0	1.41
3	Narrow-band	1.75	1.39

*Table 6: Left: Ranking of each of the mitigation methods based on Landau damping by **relevance**. Right: Ranking by global **impact**.*

R	Mitigation based on Landau damping	ave	std
1	Classical - octupole	2.87	1.36
2	2-nd order chromaticity	2.0	1.41
3	RF-Quadrupole	1.25	0.66
4	e-lenses	1.125	0.33

R	Mitigation based on Landau damping	ave	std
1	e-lenses	1.125	0.33
2	RF-Quadrupole	1.25	0.66
3	Classical - octupole	2.87	1.36
4	2-nd order chromaticity	2.0	1.41

*Table 7: Left: Ranking of each of the mitigation methods based on cooling by **relevance**. Right: Ranking by global **impact**.*

R	Mitigation based on Cooling	ave	std
2	Stochastic cooling	1.37	0.99
3	Electron cooling	1.37	0.99
4	Coherent electron cooling	1	0
5	Laser cooling	1	0

R	Mitigation based on Cooling	ave	std
1	Coherent electron cooling	1	0
2	Laser cooling	1	0
3	Stochastic cooling	1.37	0.99
4	Electron cooling	1.37	0.99

*Table 8: Left: Ranking of each of the mitigation methods based on Special Optics by **relevance**. Right: Ranking by **global impact**.*

R	Mitigation based on Special Optics	ave	std
1	Special tune	2.1	1.26
2	Special slippage	2.0	1.41
3	Negative alpha	2.0	1.5
4	Low-beta	1.5	1.0
5	Optics for mitigation instabilities	1.44	0.83
6	IBS	1.375	0.99
7	IBS suppression	1.25	0.66
8	ATS	1.25	0.66
9	IOTA	1.125	0.33

R	Mitigation based on Special Optics	ave	std
1	IOTA	1.125	0.33
2	ATS	1.25	0.66
3	IBS suppression	1.25	0.66
4	Optics for mitigation instabilities	1.44	0.83
5	IBS	1.375	0.99
6	Low-beta	1.5	1.0
7	Special slippage	2.0	1.41
8	Special tune	2.1	1.26
9	Negative alpha	2.0	1.5

4.4 COMMENTS

The above summary tables reveal that, along with established methods for mitigating the mechanisms of beam degradation, new methods are emerging.

Bunch-by-bunch feedback systems, Landau octupoles, second order chromaticity, stochastic cooling, electron cooling, lattices with special tunes and/or special momentum compaction (slippage) factor are the mitigation measures of highest relevance.

The results for the special optics sector show that approaches like IOTA, ATS, and IBS suppression lattice have a low average around 1 and also a low standard deviation. This is because these new methods are still not fully established and the community does not yet widely employ them.

Because only one participant has given a ranking on the polarization control mitigation methods, we do not proceed here on retrieving its relevance and global impact factors. The low level of response reflects the fact that this class of beam control concerns only a small minority of the laboratories.

5. Conclusions and Future plans

This deliverable report summarizes the **sources of degradation mechanisms in hadron accelerators as of early/mid 2019**. The actual ranking was provided by expert colleagues actively engaged in accelerator operation, with direct hands-on experience on the main effects afflicting their respective accelerators. Therefore, this assessment represents a state-of-the-art survey. The survey results reveal a complex landscape not easily amenable to interpretation. According to the respective laboratory and to the type of beam operation the main intensity and brightness limitations vary.

However, we can conclude that the most important intensity limitation is the **beam loss**, while **single bunch instabilities** have a wide global impact. Concerning the brightness limitations, the **nonlinearities** are the most relevant mechanism; they also account for the highest global impact. For the category called “other sources of performance limitation”, we found that again **beam loss** is the most relevant; it also has the broadest impact. We also note that UFO/dust and quenches presently are of little importance at most laboratories. We observe that both the “nonlinearities”, limiting brightness, and the beam loss, limiting intensity, are of relevance and have a significant global impact. Therefore, these two effects seem to be of the highest concern for the broadest community.

Concerning mitigation techniques, well-established methods like **bunch-by-bunch feedback**, **Landau octupoles**, and special optics with **optimised slippage factor** are still the most relevant across all laboratories. Several novel mitigation measures are being studied, but these are not yet widely deployed, and may need to be further developed.

APEC task 6.3 will carry on its activity. Starting from the reported ranking of sources of intensity and brightness limitations and from the mitigation survey results, APEC task 6.3 will use the ARIES networking capabilities to continue the discussion of advanced mitigation strategies and to draw roadmaps for further developing the various mitigation approaches. APEC will remain central to **catalysing collaborations and exploiting synergies** among several key players in the European accelerator laboratory and university landscape. All these goals will be pursued via suitable workshops, which are an integral part of the APEC work package.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ATS	Achromatic Telescopic Squeezing (optics)
DA	Dynamic Aperture
FAIR	Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research
IBS	Intra-beam Scattering
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
LLRF	Low Level Radio Frequency
RF	Radio Frequency
SC	Super conductivity
TMCI	Transverse couple mode instability
UFO	Unidentified Falling Object